

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF ANTI-CORRUPTION BEHAVIOR

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Annotation.

The article considers anti-corruption behavior as a set of conscious actions to prevent and overcome corruption situations. It is noted that the basic grounds for the formation of anti-corruption behavior, as a rule, are legal regulation and education of legal awareness in society. The main approaches to understanding the term "anti-corruption behavior", presented in the works of modern scientists, are considered.

Key words.

anti-corruption behavior, principles of anti-corruption behavior, formation of anti-corruption behavior, corruption, countering corruption.

Studying the works of researchers and specialists on this issue, it should be noted that despite the frequency of using the concept of "anti-corruption behavior", this term does not have a common understanding and essence of the phenomenon.

Most authors believe that this is the behavior of not only citizens, but also employees holding specific positions, as well as legal entities, which prevent the formation of corruption factors and corrupt activities [4]. According to S. L. Rubinshtein, the essence of anti-corruption behavior lies in the employee's personal attitude towards other people and the world around [Rubinshtein 2009: 713]. The effectiveness of its activities will depend on how developed a negative attitude towards corruption is in the management system of a particular organization.

Anti-corruption behavior is manifested in the ability of an individual to understand the cultural origins of corruption and resist corruption pressure. This behavior can be seen as an urgent need, since corruption has become widespread. In some scientific publications, anti-corruption behavior is understood as compliance with anti-corruption standards in the event that conditions for corruption arise. "Anti-Corruption Behavior" contains the following definition of anti-corruption behavior: it is a set of actions and actions of an official or a group of persons, carried out within the powers established by law, in the process of interaction between themselves and the external environment, regarding the

performance of their official duties and in order to actively counteract any manifestation of corruption. This is a set of conscious actions to prevent and overcome dangerous situations of corruption.

The main qualities of a person who observes the norms of anti-corruption behavior can be incorruptibility, determination, exactingness, openness, responsibility. Anti-corruption behavior is a set of conscious actions to prevent and overcome dangerous situations of corruption.

It should be noted that the experience of foreign countries in the formation of anti-corruption behavior is significant. For example, in America, since 1958, "administrative morality" has been introduced into the public service, which is ethical and disciplinary norms. In England, a program is being implemented to establish the principles of honesty and integrity in all spheres of society. There is even an independent advisory committee on standards of conduct in public affairs. French legislation provides for liability for such a form of corruption as patronage. It refers to the actions of officials who are in charge of the distribution of orders and provide illegal benefits to a private enterprise. The German Criminal Code expands the list of corruption offences; recommendations on compliance with the Code of Anti-Corruption Conduct are also being implemented. Finland's anti-corruption principles - transparency in the exercise of power, legitimacy of public administration, responsibility and integrity of civil servants - are enshrined in the Constitution. In Japan, since April 2000, the Law "On the Ethics of Public Officials" has been in force, there is a register of persons against whom allegations of corruption have been brought.

The study of modern problems of anti-corruption behavior can be distinguished in four main areas [Mitin 2019 129-143].

1. Socio-psychological direction. Efforts to shape anti-corruption behavior will fail if people become ingrained in the belief that law enforcement cannot be trusted and that the participation of witnesses in a trial leaves them unprotected.

Corruption can be seen as belonging to a special type of social system. In this sense, it is closely related to the size of the administrative apparatus. The desire to curb corruption and form anti-corruption behavior creates additional regulatory bodies, which again leads to the growth of corruption ties [Anti-Corruption Policy 2004: 12]. In addition, corruption is built on ordinary interpersonal relationships with friends, relatives, "confidants", "guarantors", etc. The formation of anti-corruption behavior among them is problematic: they are deeply interested in maintaining such relationships. Most often, they are not afraid of increased

criminal liability for corruption crimes, since they have already accumulated “financial fat”.

There is also an opinion that anti-corruption education should begin at school, although today's young people perceive the injustice of the distribution of life's blessings differently. In this regard, we believe that the problems of anti-corruption behavior are largely rooted in the sphere of the psyche of the individual and it is hardly possible to achieve anti-corruption behavior from employees only through the assimilation of knowledge.

Anti-corruption behavior depends on internal rules, human norms in the form of knowledge that can be applied in the performance of activities. They can be seen as a personality construct. The norms of anti-corruption behavior, acting as a personal construct, become a kind of beacon indicating the correct way of action for an employee of the organization, corresponding to his official duties.

The emergence of an anti-corruption personal construct is associated with the active formation of an idea of the norms and ideals of activity by observing the behavior of two types - corruption and anti-corruption, since all constructs, as a rule, have two poles. Polarity clearly shows what is “good” (opposing corruption) and what is “bad” (participation in corrupt activities or aiding corruption).

From a cognitive point of view, anti-corruption behavior is based on proactive thinking, which rejects the revision of views and attitudes regarding corruption. In an uncertain situation associated with the possibility of receiving a bribe, an employee must choose an anti-corruption personal construct within the framework of the “orientation - choice - execution” scheme.

In case of deviation from this construct, the employee must be aware that not only his behavior changes, but also his life and future associated with professional activity [Kiselev 2016: 49].

Thus, anti-corruption behavior in the socio-psychological aspect can be considered as a conscious and responsible performance by an employee of the organization of official duties, internal labor regulations, ethical requirements within the framework of the regulations and the rejection of corruption temptations.

2. Regulatory direction. It should be noted that success in the formation of anti-corruption behavior largely depends on the state and quality of the legal framework governing the processes of combating corruption, as well as preventive measures.

Any national legislation, as a rule, is an external reflection of social processes, the reaction of social institutions to objective reality. But the actual legal means of

combating corruption are secondary. Only by transforming the system of social relations, the totality of social, moral, economic, political and other factors, the law is able to influence corruption, its scope and significance. Anti-corruption behavior is associated with changes that must occur in the minds of people. Shaping this behavior is up to each individual. Encouragement of creative initiative, productive public discussion, intolerance to corruption offenses should become an integral part of the national culture.

3. Moral direction. The role of moral guidelines in combating corruption is discussed everywhere, they are recognized as an effective mechanism for the formation of anti-corruption behavior. It is quite difficult to assess the level of anti-corruption behavior, but in any case, there is an appeal to the norms of law, moral norms (public morality, professional ethics, group norms of corporate ethics, personal norms), business etiquette rules. Since a person works in a particular organization, anti-corruption behavior should be considered as an element of his organizational behavior. This is how a kind of moral and ethical infrastructure is formed, containing a set of tools that are used to regulate the behavior of civil servants and include anti-corruption legislation, codes of conduct, mechanisms for reporting, supervision, professional socialization, etc. ethics commissions created on a permanent basis with the involvement of independent experts. It should be noted that the implementation of moral measures in the formation of anti-corruption behavior among employees in any organization is a task of extraordinary complexity. It is important that the criteria for the effectiveness of its implementation be clearly defined, for example: the presence of documented rules and norms governing intra-organizational relations, strict adherence to them; the degree of assimilation by the employee of the norms and rules adopted in the organization; the presence of those that do not contradict the goals of the organization, the level and nature of their interaction; formation of an orderly and predictable organizational environment for employees, in which the "rules of the game" against corruption are known, transparent and stable [Mitin 2017: 347–348].

4. Economic and managerial direction. As noted, corruption and the economy are inseparable. The first parasitizes, the second creates the conditions for parasitism with imperfect legislation and the lack of conscience among those in power. In the formation of anti-corruption behavior, anti-corruption programs play an important role. The formation of anti-corruption behavior among citizens is a task of national importance, therefore, it is necessary to familiarize the persons involved in its solution with the historical prerequisites for the emergence of

corruption, forms of combating it, legal, philosophical, psychological views, and the culture of a particular historical period.

Ascertaining the studied materials on this issue, it should be noted that there are certain principles for minimizing corrupt behavior:

a) ensuring constitutionally guaranteed human rights and freedoms, their recognition, protection at the state level. Guided by this principle, one should choose a way to apply anti-corruption measures that would not violate constitutional rights and could not justify the achievement of the goal of combating corruption at any cost;

b) legitimacy of activities to minimize corrupt behavior. All participants in the process of minimizing corrupt behavior are subordinate to him and cannot ignore his requirements and take any actions not in accordance with their authority;

c) the openness of the activities of government bodies in the system of combating corruption. It is obligatory to formalize the procedures that ensure the availability of information about the activities of these bodies. Examples include the implementation of public expertise mechanisms, legal consultations, state-public information, public monitoring at the stages of preparation and decision-making, as well as ensuring the publicity of decisions made;

d) the inevitability of responsibility for committing corruption offenses (both ordinary citizens and representatives of government bodies);

e) complex use of any legal anti-corruption measures, selection of the most efficient measures, monitoring of their positive impact on the achievement of the desired result;

f) priority application of measures to prevent corruption. One of the most effective preventive measures is the open exercise by the state of power functions, supported by the system of providing services to citizens and legal entities in the "one window" mode;

g) cooperation of the state with civil society institutions, international organizations and individuals in combating corruption.

At the same time, we consider to consider one of the not unimportant facts of the formation of anti-corruption behavior - the motivational component of corruption interaction. The motivational component of any interaction contains knowledge about the internal external stimuli of the subject to activity. Internal motives include those that are dictated by the desires and needs of the subject, and external motives are those imposed on the subject from the outside. This classification is also used by many researchers to study the motives of corruption and anti-corruption interaction. In a study by D. Bailey in 1990, the purpose of

which was to study measures to combat corruption, types of internal motives were identified. These include career motives and motives of "habit" (or acceptance of corrupt interactions as a norm). Career motives include: the desire for rapid career growth, the need for respect from colleagues, the desire to improve the social level, the desire for income growth, the desire for power. Game motives were also identified (the subject perceives the situation of corrupt interaction as a game, a situation of risk and increased danger, accompanied by strong emotions and experiences that bring new strong impressions into the routine work process), self-affirmation motives as persistent grounds for the manifestation of corrupt interaction.

Game motives of corrupt interaction were also studied by Russian scientists, among which is the study of Kulikov A.Yu. His 2003 study was devoted to the motivational-volitional sphere of corrupt interaction in Russia. In the work, the research material for which was media publications about corruption crimes of officials at various levels, it is noted that the game motive is one of the main internal motives for entering into corrupt interactions. The author also suggests that the game motive is the leading one if the subject has a tendency to unlawful (including corrupt) behavior. A number of authors emphasize the danger of developing gambling motivation in situations of receiving bribes and with a tendency to corruption. Game motivation, which becomes a habit, becomes a necessary source of energy, a "working" mood, can lead to a medical dependence on receiving "additional income".

External motives include: corruption pressure and public tolerance for corruption. Public tolerance for illegal acts, not only in the area of corruption, is the subject of study and opposition in many regions of the world. This is due to the difficulties of overcoming it (tolerance) as a deep psychological and social phenomenon leading to serious consequences.

Corruption pressure is understood as a set of factors influencing the subject, leading to a situation of choice between the abuse of power for personal gain or the rejection of it. It should be noted that the path to corrupt behavior, as a norm, begins with small manifestations of the crime of legal prohibitions: up to violation of the rules of conduct in public places at school age.

Internal corruption motives include the following:

- self-interest (greed);
- career ambitions (desire to move up the career ladder);
- motive "habit".

Studying the materials and studies of a number of authors, the following features of the corruptionogenic motive of self-assertion should be noted:

-fortitude at the moment of striving for the goal (i.e., during the period when the desired position or degree of power has not yet been achieved), rather rapid fading after the goal is achieved (approval in the desired position);

- the growth of the need for material goods and the increase in their value.

Thus, the main internal motives of corrupt interaction include: self-interest, career motives, the motive of "habit", the motive of self-affirmation. The identified external motives for corrupt interaction are as follows: corrupt pressure, public example, social approval (public tolerance for offenses), social acceptance of the "comfort" of corrupt interaction, avoidance of problems and bureaucratization.

The most significant and widespread motives for corruption crimes also included:

- greed (greed);
- feeling of impunity (confidence in the absence of punishment).

As the main motives for entering into corrupt interaction, which are predominantly of an internal nature, the following are noted:

* emotional burnout. Emotional burnout is a psychological state of emotional and physical exhaustion. With regard to corrupt interaction, emotional burnout can be its predictor if the potential benefit from the former is capable, in the subject's opinion, of becoming an incentive to overcome the latter.

* components of propensity to corruption. A person prone to corruption is characterized by such features as: dissatisfaction with life, negative self-attitude, inadequate self-esteem. External conditions of instability are added to these intrapersonal characteristics.

Thus, the analysis of studies has shown that the motives of corrupt interaction can be classified on two grounds: in relation to the subject of interaction and according to the type of benefit from corruption. In relation to the subject of interaction, internal and external motives of corruption can be distinguished. The main external motives of corrupt interaction include: a public example, the comfort of corrupt interaction, tolerance for corruption (social approval), avoidance of problems (acceleration of the process), corrupt pressure. Internal motives of corrupt interaction: self-interest, career ambitions (including the motive of holding power), greed, the motive of habit, the motive of self-affirmation, the game motive, a sense of impunity. According to the type of benefit, motives associated with obtaining material benefits are distinguished: self-interest, greed (greed), a sense of impunity, tolerance for corruption. The motives associated with obtaining non-material

benefits include: career ambitions (including the retention of power), the motive of self-affirmation, the game motive.

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